

STUDY OF PLANTS ECOLOGY WITH PLANT PHYSIOLOGY THAT PRODUCE INTERESTING COMBINATIONS

Hilma Zulfa (1810422066) – Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Andalas University, Padang

This paper discusses interdisciplinary research in biological science, where at this time I chose the field of plant physiology studies with plant ecology. The specialty of the field of plant physiology is that it discusses all the internal activities of plants, both chemical and physical processes related to plant life. While the specialty of the study of plant ecology is that it can discuss specifically the interaction of plants with their environment, which is related to various natural processes and phenomena. The merging of two fields of study in a study is of course very interesting, this will increase insight both for the author himself and for the advancement of science and technology. The combination of the two studies between plant ecology and plant physiology will result in new, continuous and interesting research. In addition, the combination of these two studies can also provide applicable studies that are useful for the development of science and can be a solution for environmental remediation.

The study between plant ecology and plant physiology will produce new continuous research, this is because ecology and physiology can discuss more broadly and are interrelated with each other. An example can be seen in the application of several types and concentrations of auxin to induce rooting of bayur shoot cuttings in an effort to propagate revegetation plants. West Sumatra has an area of critical land which continues to increase every year. In 2007 the area of 409,031 ha (239,433 ha critical and very critical 169,598 ha), in 2011 the critical land area in West Sumatra increased to 509,977 ha (419,524 ha critical and 90,453 ha). With this large decrease in environmental vegetation, an effort is needed so that the soil is not further degraded, namely by means of revegetation activities which are one of the technologies to overcome damaged land (Singh, Raghubanshi and Singh, 2002). The criteria for plants used in revegetation are having high adaptability and fast growth (Iskandar, 2014). One of the plants that meet these criteria is Bayur (*Pterospermum javanicum*). Bayur is a type of tree that belongs to the Sterculiaceae family and requires light for its growth (Martini, 2001). To support the success of land revegetation, the availability of plant material in large quantities is required. Shoot cuttings are one of the vegetative propagation techniques that have been used for mass propagation of several types of plants. Propagation of shoot cuttings comes from relatively juvenile material with a maximum level of cell differentiation. This is evidenced by the research conducted by Sumbayak et al., (2014) propagation of ramin by shoot cuttings resulted in a percentage of cuttings of more than 95%. One of the factors that influence the success rate of cuttings is growth hormone which can induce the formation of roots and shoots. To meet the growth hormone for root formation, root-promoting hormones are used, especially from the Auxin group. Growth regulators classified as Auxins are Indole Acetic Acid (IAA), Indole-3-butyric acid acid (IBA), -Naphthalene Acetic Acid (NAA) and 2,4 Dichlorophenoxyacetic (2,4-D) (Wudianto, 1998). The type and concentration of auxin will give a different response to the roots. Several research results on the effect of growth regulators on the growth of cuttings have been reported, namely the administration of 100 ppm NAA was able to increase the percentage of sprouting, percentage of rooted and percentage of root dry weight compared to control on shoot cuttings of Meranti Tembaga (Djamhuri, 2011). Administration of 200 ppm NAA was able to produce root and shoot growth of Apokad (*Persea Americana* Mill.) cuttings (Febriana,

2009). Giving IAA concentration of 100 ppm was able to produce better root growth in Teak (*Tectona grandis* Linn. f.). According to the results of research Irwanto (2001), stated that the best use of IBA on shoot cuttings of Miranti Putih (*Shorea asamica* D.) was achieved at a concentration of 100 ppm. In the study of Danu, Subiakto and Putri (2010), using IBA with a concentration of 200 ppm gave good results on the growth of Damar (*Agathi loranthifolia* Salisb.) shoot cuttings.

In addition, the combination of plant ecology studies with plant physiology can also provide applicable studies that are useful for the development of science and can be a solution for environmental remediation. An example can be seen from research on the growth of Surian seedlings inoculated with mycorrhizae on ultisol soil planting media. Surian [(*Toona sinensis* (Juss.) M. Roem.)] is one of the higher plants found in Indonesia. This plant belongs to the Meliaceae family. Surian is a versatile plant, nowadays many people use this plant for various purposes. The wood is used for building materials and the roots are used as materials for treatment such as chronic diarrheal diseases, dysentery and other intestinal diseases, the shoots of the leaves of Surian can also be used to treat swelling of the kidneys (Yuhernita & Juniarti, 2009). Surian plants have high economic value and are preferred by the community to be used as building materials. The demand for this type of wood is increasing, especially for the manufacture of furniture, interior rooms, cabinets, door and window frames (Djam'an, 2003). Surian also has the potential to be used as a type of rehabilitation plant for degraded land (Sofyan & Islam, 2006). The success of planting activities is closely related to success at the nursery level in the nursery, but there are several obstacles faced in the procurement of Surian seeds, including the lack of quality seed information and the quality testing of Surian seeds has not been widely carried out (Djam'an & Dharmawati, 2002). To be able to grow well, Surian plants require natural media in the form of soil rich in nutrients, but not all soils contain complete nutrients, one example is ultisol soil. Ultisols are a common type of soil found in tropical climates. In Indonesia, Ultisols are spread over an area of 25% of the total land area of Indonesia. The weakness of ultisol soil is that it has high acidity because the bases supporting soil fertility such as Ca, K, and Mg have been washed away during the development of ultisol or used by plants growing on it. Ultisol soil has a pH <5.5 (Prasetyo & Suriadikarta, 2006). Ultisol soil conditions that have a low pH and lack of nutrients cause plants that live in Ultisol soil areas to become less fertile (Margarettha, 2007). Lack of nutrients in Ultisol soil can affect the growth of plant seeds. One alternative that can be used to fulfill these nutrient needs, use microorganisms that are able to associate with plants, such as AMF. Mycorrhizae is a form of mutualism symbiosis between fungi and higher plant roots. The role of AMF in increasing plant growth and production has been widely reported and from the results of recent studies there have been many reports containing the application and production of commercially cultivated AMF inoculants. The use of mycorrhizae lately is often used to increase plant growth. The potential of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) symbiosis with plants is very important to be used for cultivation purposes, especially during nurseries which can help growth and planting in the field (Corryanti & Rohayati, 2000). Plant symbiosis with AMF can increase soil nutrient absorption and root resistance to drought, protect roots from disease attacks, supply additional growth hormones and growth regulators (ZPT) as well as benefits in increasing plant resistance to root pathogen attacks. Several factors that influence the success rate of the use of mycorrhizae for growth are the type of mycorrhizae itself and the dosage. The dose of AMF for growth varies depending on the type of plant.

Interdisciplinary research is very useful for science, especially in the study of plant ecology with plant physiology. The combination of the study of plant ecology with plant physiology will result in continuous new research. In addition, the combination of these two studies can also provide applicable studies that are useful for the development of science and can be a solution for environmental remediation.

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